

Leveraging Single-Page Applications for Seamless Scientific Workflows: DevSecOps Considerations

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Abstract—Single-page applications (SPAs) have become indispensable in modern frontend development, with widespread adoption in scientific applications. The process of creating a single-page web application development environment which accurately reflects the production environment isn't always straightforward. Most SPA build systems assume configuration at build time, while DevSecOps engineers prefer runtime configuration. This paper suggests a framework-agnostic approach to address issues that encompass both development and deployment, but are difficult to tackle without knowledge in both domains.

Index Terms—Content Security Policy, DevSecOps, Docker, frontend, single-page application, security

I. INTRODUCTION

Single-page applications (SPAs) have become crucial components of modern frontend development, including scientific applications like INTERSECT (Interconnected Scientific Ecosystem) [1] software framework. SPAs play a pivotal role in the scientific software community, benefiting users, research software engineers, and fostering collaboration. By offering a seamless and interactive experience, SPAs empower users to navigate complex scientific workflows and analyze data without disruptive page reloads. Real-time updates and state preservation ensure a continuous user experience throughout the entire workflow.

Frontend applications, like backend applications, have environment-dependent variables like URLs to server-side APIs or a base URL to allow an SPA's URL routing logic to work with deployment behind any reverse proxy path. In containerized environments, DevSecOps engineers often define these variables at runtime instead of build time, enabling reuse of build artifacts across multiple deployments. This is important, as many scientific applications utilize multiple deployments across multiple isolated scientific ecosystems.

When deploying a single-page web application, leveraging a static file server such as NGINX has benefits over utilizing server-side rendering (i.e. with Express), such as performance

and simplified server configuration. The static server approach also makes it easier to potentially leverage cloud object storage systems in the future, such as Amazon S3. Certain server-side properties, such as a strong Content Security Policy (CSP), should be configured at runtime, with the basic structure established at build time. This approach is frontend framework agnostic, and while this paper focuses on using NGINX, any static file server, such as Apache HTTPD, can be used.

II. FRONTEND APPLICATION SETUP

A solid frontend setup maintains consistency across environments and reduces the need for control flow statements to check the application's mode (development or production). Developers and testers aim to modify environment variables easily without making changes in multiple locations, while production environments need fast deployment verification. This section recommends creating a config object on the global Window object [2] (`window.config`) to access variables, utilizing a separate file (`config.js`) to define variables, and leveraging existing frontend toolsets to simplify developer workflows.

A. The `window.config` object: To access runtime-defined variables in frontend JavaScript code, use the `window.config` object. This approach consolidates all environment variables in one statement, provides a unified configuration interface, and aids in locating API calls in the source code.

B. The `config.js` file: Import a generic configuration file called `config.js` in the `index.html` file before any other JavaScript code. In development, the file should exist but be empty. In production, this file is created from Docker environment variables and defines the `window.config` object.

C. Developer workflows: Many single-page application (SPA) build systems, such as Create-React-App [3] or Vite [4], use `.env` files to inject environment variables in development environments. However, in production builds, it's better to avoid injecting environment variables at build time. Many build systems can strip out code wrapped inside environment-based conditional blocks. Start the application code with a development-specific conditional block to create the `window.config` object from the injected environment variables. This ensures the code is removed in the production build, reduces conditionals, and prevents exposure of development details.

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III. WEB SERVER AND DOCKER CONTAINER CONFIGURATION

This section focuses on serving the SPA via a static web server in a Docker container.

A. *Content Security Policy*: Cross-site scripting – the ability to inject attacker-controlled code into the context of a web application - is one of the most dangerous and common web vulnerabilities [5]. A properly configured CSP helps prevent malicious code from executing. CSP statements should be set via server-side HTTP Headers, instead of the HTML `<meta>` tag. It allows for the dynamic configuration as advocated by this paper, the usage of the "frame-ancestors" directive instead of the deprecated "X-Frame-Options" header [6] for clickjacking protection, and using the "report-to" directive to log instances of attempted CSP violations. To reuse the same builds across multiple execution environments, the "connect-src" directive should be customized per deployment. Certain environment variables will signify a backend API; each of these variables will influence the directive generation. See Figure 1 as an example of an Nginx CSP statement which will be modified by environment variables.

B. *Building the Docker Container*: We start with the default NGINX container and customize it. The customized server configuration includes the "Content-Security-Policy" header with placeholders for environment variables. The "connect-src" statement in the header contains the "self" directive by default to allow requests from the same origin. Next, we add an entrypoint shell script to finalize the frontend environment and server configuration using environment variables. Finally, we remove any default HTML files and add the compiled frontend source code to the root HTML directory.

C. *Docker entrypoint scripts*: We take advantage of the NGINX Docker container's capability to execute predefined entrypoint shell scripts before starting the primary NGINX process. During the container build, we add a shell script to the "/docker-entrypoint.d/" directory. The container's entrypoint script executes these scripts sequentially based on the sorted names of the files. In the script, we use environment variables to generate the config.js file and the connect-src statement of the CSP. If an environment variable represents an absolute-path URL to call the backend, there is no need to add an additional source in "connect-src" as the 'self' directive already covers it. See Figure 2 as an example of an excerpt from an entrypoint script.

IV. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE: INTERSECT USE CASE

To illustrate the framework-agnostic approach for developing and deploying SPAs, let's consider the INTERSECT use case. In this use case, users can construct scientific campaigns by calling multiple scientific services, such as a microscope or a 3D printer. The frontend application enables users to view a graph of all services, manage campaigns, launch campaigns, and view system-wide broker messages associated with their campaigns. The SPA allows seamless navigation across multiple views without reinitializing data streams.

The frontend application relies on environment variables to determine the base URL and URLs for different backend services. The URLs are referenced using the window.config object, which provides a single interface for accessing these variables. The config.js file defines the window.config object and is dynamically generated based on the environment variables during container startup.

For the INTERSECT usecase, Figure 2 demonstrates a Docker entrypoint script that is responsible for updating the Content Security Policy (CSP) configuration and generating the config.js file using the provided environment variables. This script ensures the secure execution of the application and allows for customization based on specific deployment requirements. Figure 1 showcases the INTERSECT Nginx configuration file with a dynamic CSP line, where placeholders enclosed in double curly braces are replaced at runtime by corresponding environment variables. This dynamic configuration capability enables the reuse of the same build across multiple deployment environments within the INTERSECT use case.

```
add_header Content-Security-Policy "default-src 'none';
frame-ancestors 'none'; base-uri 'none'; form-action '
none'; style-src 'self'; script-src 'self'; connect-src
'self' {{API_URL}} {{API_B_URL}}; img-src 'self'"
always;
```

Figure 1. CSP line in INTERSECT Nginx config file for script mentioned in Figure 2, added as-is to the Nginx configuration directory.

```
#!/bin/sh
set -eu # fail if env. variable not set
readonly CNF="/etc/nginx/conf.d/security.conf"
edit_security_conf() {
HOOK=$1
VALUE=$2
case $VALUE in
"/"*)
# absolute path, so don't need to add anything to CSP (
just remove the hook)
sed -i "s[[[:space:]]*{{HOOK}}]~"~g" $CNF
;;
*)
# external URL, need to add the URL to CSP
sed -i "s~{{HOOK}}~${VALUE%/}/~g" $CNF
;;
esac
}
BASE_URL_RESOLVED=${BASE_URL:-}
# update CSP
edit_security_conf "API_URL" "${API_URL}"
edit_security_conf "API_B_URL" "${API_B_URL}"
# Create config.js from environment variables
cat<<!EOF! > /usr/share/nginx/html/config.js
window['config']={
baseUrl: '${BASE_URL_RESOLVED%/}',
apiUrl: '${API_URL%/}',
apiBurl: '${API_B_URL%/}',};
!EOF!
```

Figure 2. INTERSECT Docker entrypoint script, runs on container startup.

V. CONCLUSION

We present a framework-agnostic approach for developing and deploying SPAs, with a strong focus on DevSecOps considerations. Our solution addresses the challenges of accurately reflecting the production environment during SPA development and deployment, as well as accommodating runtime environment variables and dynamic CSP configurations. We have successfully used this approach in several applications, such as INTERSECT [1].

REFERENCES

- [1] A. M. Thakur, S. Hitefield, M. McDonnell, M. Wolf, R. Archibald, L. Drane, K. Roccapriore, M. Ziatdinov, J. McGaha, R. Smith, J. Hetrick, M. Abraham, S. Yakubov, G. Watson, B. Chance, C. Nguyen, M. Baker, R. Michael, E. Arenholz, and B. Mintz, "Towards a software development framework for interconnected science ecosystems," in *Accelerating Science and Engineering Discoveries Through Integrated Research Infrastructure for Experiment, Big Data, Modeling and Simulation*, K. Doug, G. Al, S. Pophale, H. Liu, and S. Parete-Koon, Eds. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022, pp. 206–224.
- [2] MDN Web Docs, "Window," <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/Window>, May 4, (Accessed on 05/04/2023).
- [3] Create React App, "Adding custom environment variables," <https://create-react-app.dev/docs/adding-custom-environment-variables/>, May 4, (Accessed on 05/04/2023).
- [4] ViteJS, "Env variables and modes," <https://vitejs.dev/guide/env-and-mode.html>, May 4, (Accessed on 05/04/2023).
- [5] L. Weichselbaum, M. Spagnuolo, S. Lekies, and A. Janc, "Csp is dead, long live csp! on the insecurity of whitelists and the future of content security policy," in *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, Vienna, Austria, 2016.
- [6] MDN Web Docs, "X-frame-options," <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Headers/X-Frame-Options#directives>, May 4, (Accessed on 05/04/2023).